

Horizon 2020

Call: H2020-MSCA-IF-2016
(Marie Skłodowska-Curie Individual Fellowships)

Topic: MSCA-IF-2016

Type of action: MSCA-IF-EF-ST
(Standard EF)

Proposal number: 746216

Proposal acronym: MARBAL

Deadline Id: H2020-MSCA-IF-2016

Table of contents

<i>Section</i>	<i>Title</i>	<i>Action</i>
1	General information	
2	Participants & contacts	
3	Budget	
4	Ethics	
5	Call-specific questions	

How to fill in the forms?

The administrative forms must be filled in for each proposal using the templates available in the submission system. Some data fields in the administrative forms are pre-filled based on the previous steps in the submission wizard.

Proposal ID **746216**

Acronym **MARBAL**

1 - General information

Topic MSCA-IF-2016

Call Identifier H2020-MSCA-IF-2016

Type of Action MSCA-IF-EF-ST

Deadline Id H2020-MSCA-IF-2016

Acronym

Proposal title

Note that for technical reasons, the following characters are not accepted in the Proposal Title and will be removed: < > " &

Duration in months

Scientific Area

Please select up to 5 descriptors (and at least 3) that best characterise the subject of your proposal, in descending order of relevance.

Descriptor 1

Descriptor 2

Descriptor 3

Free keywords

Proposal ID **746216**

Acronym **MARBAL**

Abstract

MARBAL will integrate human osteology with isotopic analyses of diet and mobility, osteobiographical reconstructions of the lives of prehistoric individuals, and archaeological analyses of material culture. The project aim is to investigate how Early Bronze Age (2700-2200 BC) mortuary practices shaped, and were shaped by, emerging regional trade networks and the establishment and negotiation of community identities in the Apuseni mountain region of Romania. The research objectives are: 1) To understand the social factors that made individuals eligible for kinds of mortuary treatment, to ascertain whether eligibility for burial was affected by aspects of social identity; 2) To investigate the intersection of social and bioarchaeological inequalities, and 3) To reconstruct community social interactions. These objectives will be achieved by providing training for the EF in 1) osteobiographical and 2) isotopic analyses, while collecting and analyzing osteoarchaeological data from the site of Rameț-Gugului. MARBAL will contribute to our understanding of the ways in which mortuary practices can be used to shape community and individual identities and dampen or enhance living social inequalities. It will take place at the University of Cambridge where relevant scientific, regional and period specialisms abound.

Remaining characters

672

Has this proposal (or a very similar one) been submitted to a Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Individual Fellowship call? Yes No

Proposal ID **746216**

Acronym **MARBAL**

Declarations

1) The applicant (future beneficiary) declares to have the explicit consent of all partner organisations (if applicable) on their participation and on the content of this proposal.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
2) The information contained in this proposal is correct and complete.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
3) This proposal complies with ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity — as set out, for instance, in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity — and including, in particular, avoiding fabrication, falsification, plagiarism or other research misconduct).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
4) The applicant (future beneficiary) confirms:	
- to have carried out the self-check of the financial capacity of the organisation on https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/organisations/lfv.html or to be covered by a financial viability check in an EU project for the last closed financial year. Where the result was “weak” or “insufficient”, the applicant (future beneficiary) confirms being aware of the measures that may be imposed in accordance with the H2020 Grants Manual (Chapter on Financial capacity check); or	<input type="radio"/>
- is exempt from the financial capacity check being a public body including international organisations, higher or secondary education establishment or a legal entity, whose viability is guaranteed by a Member State or associated country, as defined in the H2020 Grants Manual (Chapter on Financial capacity check); or	<input type="radio"/>
- as sole participant in the proposal is exempt from the financial capacity check.	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
5) The applicant (future beneficiary) hereby declares:	
- it is fully eligible in accordance with the criteria set out in the specific call for proposals; and	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- it has the financial and operational capacity to carry out the proposed action.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
The applicant (future beneficiary) is only responsible for the correctness of the information relating to his/her own organisation. Where the proposal to be retained for EU funding, the applicant (future beneficiary) will be required to present a formal declaration in this respect.	

According to Article 131 of the Financial Regulation of 25 October 2012 on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the Union (Official Journal L 298 of 26.10.2012, p. 1) and Article 145 of its Rules of Application (Official Journal L 362, 31.12.2012, p.1) applicants found guilty of misrepresentation may be subject to administrative and financial penalties under certain conditions.

Personal data protection

Your reply to the grant application will involve the recording and processing of personal data (such as your name, address and CV), which will be processed pursuant to Regulation (EC) No 45/2001 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data by the Community institutions and bodies and on the free movement of such data. Unless indicated otherwise, your replies to the questions in this form and any personal data requested are required to assess your grant application in accordance with the specifications of the call for proposals and will be processed solely for that purpose. Details concerning the processing of your personal data are available on the [privacy statement](#). Applicants may lodge a complaint about the processing of their personal data with the European Data Protection Supervisor at any time.

Your personal data may be registered in the Early Warning System (EWS) only or both in the EWS and Central Exclusion Database (CED) by the Accounting Officer of the Commission, should you be in one of the situations mentioned in:

- the Commission Decision 2008/969 of 16.12.2008 on the Early Warning System (for more information see the [Privacy Statement](#)), or
- the Commission Regulation 2008/1302 of 17.12.2008 on the Central Exclusion Database (for more information see the [Privacy Statement](#)).

Proposal ID **746216**

Acronym **MARBAL**

List of participants

#	Participant Legal Name	Country
1	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE	United Kingdom

Proposal ID **746216**

Acronym **MARBAL**

Short name **THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHO**

2 - Administrative data of participating organisations

Future Host Institution

PIC	Legal name
999977172	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE

Short name: *THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE*

Street TRINITY LANE THE OLD SCHOOLS

Town CAMBRIDGE

Postcode CB2 1TN

Country United Kingdom

Webpage www.cam.ac.uk

Legal Status of your organisation

Research and Innovation legal statuses

Public body yes

Legal person yes

Non-profit yes

International organisation no

International organisation of European interest no

Secondary or Higher education establishment yes

Research organisation yes

Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) no

Academic Sector yes

NACE Code: 853 - Higher education

Does this participant deliver doctoral degrees that are recognised as such by the relevant national authorities?

Yes No

Proposal ID **746216**

Acronym **MARBAL**

Short name **THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHO**

Department(s) carrying out the proposed work

Department 1

Department name not applicable

Same as organisation address

Street

Town

Postcode

Country

If the location of the Department carrying out the proposed work is not the same as the location of the Host Institute, please note that although the proposal submission system calculates the budget of the project based on the location of the Host Institute, the budget of the project for the grant agreement will be calculated by using the country coefficient of the location of the Department carrying out the proposed work.

Proposal ID **746216**

Acronym **MARBAL**

Short name **THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHO**

Researcher

The name and e-mail of the Researcher and Supervisor are read-only in the administrative form, only additional details can be edited here. To give access rights and contact details of contact persons, please go back to Step 4 of the submission wizard and save the changes.

Researcher ID	0000-0002-7387-2307		
Last Name*	BECK	Last Name at Birth	BECK
First Name(s)*	Jessica	Gender*	<input type="radio"/> Male <input checked="" type="radio"/> Female
Title	Dr.	Country of residence*	United States
Nationality*	United States	Nationality 2	
Date of Birth (DD/MM/YYYY)	11/10/1987	Country of Birth*	United States
		Place of Birth	California, United States

Contact address

Current organisation name	University of Pittsburgh		
Current Department/Faculty/Institute/ Laboratory name	Center for Comparative Archaeology		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Same as organisation address		
Street	3302 Posvar Hall		
Postcode/Cedex	15260	Town	Pittsburgh
Phone	+17346786681	Country	United States
Phone2 / Mobile	+xxx xxxxxxxxxxxx		
E-Mail*	jessbeck@umich.edu		

Proposal ID **746216** Acronym **MARBAL** Short name **THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHO**

Qualifications

University Degree	Date of award (DD/MM/YYYY)	<input type="text" value="01/05/2008"/>
Doctorate (in progress)	Date of award (DD/MM/YYYY)	<input type="text"/>
Doctorate	Date of award (DD/MM/YYYY)	<input type="text" value="19/08/2016"/>
Full time postgraduate research experience	Number of months	<input type="text" value="1"/>
Other Academic qualifications	Date of award (DD/MM/YYYY)	<input type="text"/>

Place of activity/place of residence (previous 5 years - most recent one first)

Indicate the period(s) and the country/countries in which you have legally resided and/or had your main activity (work, studies, etc) during the last 5 years up until the deadline for the submission of the proposal. Please fill in this section without gaps, until the call deadline (14/09/2016).

Period from	Period to	Duration (days)	Country
01/09/2011	14/09/2016	1841	United States
Total		1841	

Proposal ID **746216**

Acronym **MARBAL**

Short name **THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHO**

Supervisor

The name and e-mail of the Researcher and Supervisor are read-only in the administrative form, only additional details can be edited here. To give access rights and contact details of contact persons, please go back to Step 4 of the submission wizard and save the changes.

Title

Sex Male Female

First name* **John**

Last name* **Robb**

E-Mail* **jer39@cam.ac.uk**

Position in org.

Department

Same as organisation address

Street

Town

Post code

Country

Website

Phone

Phone 2

Fax

Other contact persons

First Name	Last Name	E-mail	Phone
Renata	Schaeffer	h2020@admin.cam.ac.uk	+441223333543

Proposal ID **746216**

Acronym **MARBAL**

3 - Budget

Is the Researcher eligible for family allowance? Yes No

Participant Number	Organisation Short Name	Country	Country Coefficient	Number of Months	Researcher Unit Cost			Institutional Unit Cost		Total
					Living Allowance	Mobility Allowance	Family Allowance	Research, training and networking costs	Management and Overheads	
1	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE	UK	1,203	24	134254,80	14400,00	0,00	19200,00	15600,00	183454,80
Total				24	134254,80	14400,00	0,00	19200,00	15600,00	183454,80

Partner Organisation from Third Country does not sign the Grant Agreement, does not recruit the researcher and does not directly claim costs from the action. The entire EC contribution is transmitted to the Host organisation located in Members States or Associated Countries.

4 - Ethics issues table

1. HUMAN EMBRYOS/FOETUSES		Page
Does your research involve Human Embryonic Stem Cells (hESCs) ?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Does your research involve the use of human embryos?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Does your research involve the use of human foetal tissues / cells?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
2. HUMANS		Page
Does your research involve human participants?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Does your research involve physical interventions on the study participants?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
3. HUMAN CELLS / TISSUES		Page
Does your research involve human cells or tissues (other than from Human Embryos/ Foetuses, i.e. section 1)?	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	p.20
Are they available commercially?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Are they obtained within this project?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Are they obtained from another project, laboratory or institution?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Are they obtained from biobank?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
4. PERSONAL DATA		Page
Does your research involve personal data collection and/or processing?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Does your research involve further processing of previously collected personal data (secondary use)?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
5. ANIMALS		Page
Does your research involve animals?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
6. THIRD COUNTRIES		Page
In case non-EU countries are involved, do the research related activities undertaken in these countries raise potential ethics issues?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Do you plan to use local resources (e.g. animal and/or human tissue samples, genetic material, live animals, human remains, materials of historical value, endangered fauna or flora samples, etc.)?	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	p.20

Proposal ID **746216**

Acronym **MARBAL**

Do you plan to import any material - including personal data - from non-EU countries into the EU?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Do you plan to export any material - including personal data - from the EU to non-EU countries?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
In case your research involves low and/or lower middle income countries , are any benefits-sharing actions planned?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Could the situation in the country put the individuals taking part in the research at risk?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
7. ENVIRONMENT & HEALTH and SAFETY		Page
Does your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Does your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Does your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
8. DUAL USE		Page
Does your research involve dual-use items in the sense of Regulation 428/2009, or other items for which an authorisation is required?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
9. EXCLUSIVE FOCUS ON CIVIL APPLICATIONS		Page
Could your research raise concerns regarding the exclusive focus on civil applications?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
10. MISUSE		Page
Does your research have the potential for misuse of research results?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
11. OTHER ETHICS ISSUES		Page
Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	

I confirm that I have taken into account all ethics issues described above and that, if any ethics issues apply, I will complete the ethics self-assessment and attach the required documents.

[How to Complete your Ethics Self-Assessment](#)

Proposal ID **746216**

Acronym **MARBAL**

5 - Call specific questions

Eligibility Researcher (future fellow)

1. Were you in the last 5 years in military service?

Yes No

Other Questions

For communication purposes only, the REA asks for permission to publish the name of the researcher (future fellow) should the proposal be retained for funding.

1. Does the researcher (future fellow) give this permission?

Yes No

2. Is there a secondment in Member States or Associated Countries envisaged in Part B of this proposal?

Yes No

Proposal ID **746216**

Acronym **MARBAL**

Data management activities

A new focus within Horizon 2020 is data management, for example through the use of [Data Management Plan \(DMP\)](#).

DMPs detail what data the project will generate, whether and how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and re-use, and how it will be curated and preserved.

The use of a DMP is required for projects participating in the Open Research Data Pilot in the form of a deliverable in the first 6 months of the project (possible updates during the project).

Other projects are invited to submit a DMP if relevant for their planned research.

Are data management activities relevant for your proposed project?	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No
A Data Management Plan will be delivered (Please note: a Data Management Plan (DMP) is required for projects participating in the Open Research Data Pilot in Horizon 2020, in the form of a deliverable in the first 6 months of the project. All other projects may deliver a DMP on a voluntary basis, if relevant for their research).	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Data Management is part of a Work Package.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Data Management will be integrated in another way.	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Please indicate how data management will be addressed in your project:		
<i>Please indicate how data management will be addressed in your project.</i>		

Open Research Data Pilot in Horizon 2020

All applicants can participate in the [Pilot on Open Research Data in Horizon 2020](#)¹ on a voluntary basis. This Pilot aims to improve and maximise access to and re-use of research data generated by actions.

Participants in the Pilot will be invited to formulate a Data Management Plan (DMP). DMPs detail what data the project will generate, whether and how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and re-use, and how it will be curated and preserved.

Participating in the Pilot is flexible in the sense that it does not mean that all research data needs to be open. Rather, projects can define certain datasets to remain closed via a Data Management Plan (DMP).

Please note that participation in this Pilot does not constitute part of the evaluation process. Proposals will not be evaluated favourably because they participate in the Pilot on a voluntary basis.

We wish to participate in the Pilot on Open Research Data in Horizon 2020 on a voluntary basis	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input checked="" type="radio"/> No
--	---------------------------	-------------------------------------

¹ According to article 43.2 of Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council, of 11 December 2013, laying down the rules for participation and dissemination in "Horizon 2020 - the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020)" and repealing Regulation (EC) No 1906/2006.

START PAGE

MARIE SKŁODOWSKA-CURIE ACTIONS

Individual Fellowships (IF) Call: H2020-MSCA-IF-2016

PART B

“MARBAL”

“Mortuary Archaeology of the Rameț Bronze Age Landscape: Identity and inequality in early mining communities (2700-2200 BC)”

Map 1: Bronze Age sites across the area of investigation in southwest Transylvania. Map courtesy of Colin Quinn.

This proposal is to be evaluated as:

Standard EF

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Table of Contents

List of Participating Organizations

1. EXCELLENCE	4
1.1 Quality and credibility of the research/innovation action (level of novelty, appropriate consideration of inter/multidisciplinary and gender aspects)	4
Introduction, state-of-the-art, objectives and overview of the action.....	4
Research methodology and approach:.....	4
Originality and innovative aspects of the research program.....	5
1.2 Quality and appropriateness of the training and of the two way transfer of knowledge between the researcher and the host	5
New knowledge gained by the experienced researcher:	6
Transfer of knowledge to the host institution	6
1.3 Quality of the supervision and of the integration in the team/institution	7
Qualifications and experience of the supervisor.....	7
Hosting arrangements	7
2. IMPACT	8
2.1 Enhancing the potential and future career prospects of the researcher	8
Impact of planned research and training on career prospects of experienced researcher	8
Acquisition of new competencies:	8
2.2 Quality of the proposed measures to exploit and disseminate the action results	9
2.3 Quality of the proposed measures to communicate the action activities to different target audiences	9
3. QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY OF THE IMPLEMENTATION	10
3.1 Coherence and effectiveness of the work plan	10
3.2. Appropriateness of the allocation of tasks and resources	12
3.3 Appropriateness of the management structure and procedures, including risk management	12
Organization and management structure	12
Risk mitigation strategy	13
3.4 Appropriateness of the institutional environment (infrastructure)	13
B4. Curriculum Vitae of the Experienced Researcher	14
B5. Capacity of the Participating Organisations	18
B6. Ethical Issues	19

List of Participating Organisations

Participating organisations	Legal Entity Short Name	Academic (tick)	Non-academic (tick)	Country	Dept./ Division / Laboratory	Supervisor	Role of Partner Organisation
<u>Beneficiary</u>							
- The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Cambridge	UCAM	X		United Kingdom	McDonald Institute for Archaeological Research	Professor Dr. John Robb	

1. EXCELLENCE

1.1 Quality and credibility of the research/innovation action (level of novelty, appropriate consideration of inter/multidisciplinary and gender aspects)

Introduction, state-of-the-art, objectives and overview of the action: The multidisciplinary project MARBAL examines the impact of the emergence of inequality on Early Bronze Age individuals using human skeletal analysis. In conjunction with the Rameț archaeological project, it will integrate human osteology (osteoarchaeological analysis of the age, sex, and health), stable isotope analyses of human diet and mobility, archaeological analyses of material culture (grave goods) and spatial analysis (archaeological survey at a micro- and macro-scale) to investigate how Early Bronze Age (EBA) (2700-2200 BC) mortuary practices shaped, and were shaped by, emerging regional trade networks and the establishment and negotiation of community identities in the Apuseni mountain region of Romania. The Bronze Age (c. 2700 to 600 BC) is marked by the emergence of social hierarchy across multiple regions of Europe. The Apuseni Mountains of southwest Transylvania, Romania, are amongst the richest gold and copper procurement zones in the world. Metals here were heavily exploited and traded widely across Europe during the Bronze Age. Communities constructed highly visible mounded tombs in the mountains, potentially to establish and contest access to metal resources. Archaeological survey has identified at least 100 Bronze Age cemeteries in the region. To date, no cemeteries have been fully excavated, though previous small-scale excavation has shown variability in the mortuary treatment of interred individuals that may be related to identity and social status. The MARBAL project will be undertaken in conjunction with the Rameț archaeological project which entails the excavation of Rameț-Gugului, an EBA cemetery containing seven tombs of variable size. MARBAL is not part of the Rameț project but rather supplements it by providing training for an Experienced Researcher (ER, Dr Jess Beck) in new skills which will not only improve her career prospects but will also help to shed light on the later prehistory of a region of Eastern Europe which until recently has not received the attention it deserves. The site is located along a path between rich copper and gold sources and the Mureș River, the main interregional trade route during the Bronze Age. The Rameț project is co-directed by archaeologist Colin Quinn (University of Michigan), an archaeologist who has conducted extensive survey in southwest Transylvania, and undertaken in collaboration with Horia Ciugudean and the Muzeul Național al Unirii-Alba Iulia. While the Rameț project is concerned with a larger mortuary and landscape analysis of this Early Bronze Age cemetery, the goal of MARBAL is to analyse the human remains recovered from the site using cutting edge osteoarchaeological techniques. The multidisciplinary MARBAL project will draw upon osteoarchaeological analysis of age, sex and palaeopathology, carbon and nitrogen isotope analyses of diet, strontium and oxygen isotope analyses of mobility, and AMS radiocarbon dating. The purpose of the MARBAL project is to combine traditional osteoarchaeological studies with novel stable isotope analyses and osteobiographical approaches. The combination of osteoarchaeological evidence of identity with stable isotope analyses will allow the ER to construct nuanced ‘osteobiographies’ of the individuals buried at Rameț-Gugului, using multiple lines of skeletal evidence to develop an understanding of how competition for metal resources affected people’s daily lives in prehistory and led to the emergence of inequality. Such an interdisciplinary approach is state-of-the-art in Romania given that very few EBA cemeteries have been excavated to date. Similarly, using cutting edge isotopic and osteobiographical analyses will provide new insight into prehistory in this region. These multiple lines of evidence will be interpreted in a theoretical framework that explores the degree of coherence or dissonance between various archaeological domains¹, specifically examining the extent to which ‘performed’ mortuary practices are used to either dampen or enhance ‘living’ social inequalities. The ER will apply the training in isotopic analysis and osteobiography to both new and existing materials. The analysis and training involved will not only further the career prospects of the ER, it will also enhance the work of Romanian archaeologist Horia Ciugudean and the Muzeul Național al Unirii-Alba Iulia at the site and across the region.

Research objectives, methodology and approach: MARBAL aims to investigate how emerging social inequalities were materialized in human bodies and contested through mortuary performance in one of the richest mining landscapes in EBA Europe. It contributes to an understanding of the origin and maintenance of social inequalities, a major theme in contemporary archaeological research². The primary research goal is to develop a multidisciplinary approach to the origins of prehistoric inequality that integrates the new data from human skeletal remains to be obtained during the EF, with analyses of material culture and spatial studies of cemetery location and organization which will use as yet unpublished data available to the ER from the Rameț project. This research goal is developed to

¹ Quinn, C. and J. Beck. 2016. Essential tensions in mortuary contexts: Exploring inequality through bioarchaeology. *Open Archaeology*, Topical Issue in Bioarchaeology. 2:18-41.

² Price, T.D., and G.M. Feinman (eds.) (2014) *Pathways to power: New perspectives on the emergence of social inequality*. New York: Springer.

situate mortuary politics in Transylvania within a larger spatial and temporal context involving early mining technology, the growing importance of long distance exchange, and the development of centralized polities with institutionalized inequality. The social organization of EBA communities in the Apuseni region remains poorly understood. The research has implications for our knowledge of the emergence of social inequalities in regions with controlled and/or contested resources (e.g. raw materials, subsistence, water) and contributes to recent research on how political and economic inequalities intersect with the control of key economic resources³. This research goal will be accomplished by achieving three main research objectives (ROs 1-3): understanding the social factors that made individuals eligible for kinds of mortuary treatment (RO1), investigating the intersection of social and biological inequalities (RO2) and analysing regional community interactions (RO3). The research objectives will be realized through a series of work packages (WP), dissemination deliverables (D) and milestones (M) described in section 3.1.

RO1 – To understand the social factors that made individuals eligible for kinds of mortuary treatment, to ascertain whether eligibility for burial was affected by aspects of social identity: In order to reconstruct how early mining communities were organized, we must first examine which individuals were eligible for burial. Was burial restricted by age, sex or membership of social groups? The limited number of tumuli constructed in each cemetery suggests the restriction of mortuary treatment to a specific subset of individuals. Bioarchaeological analysis of the age (through dental development and wear, epiphyseal fusion, and assessment of the auricular surface, pubic symphysis, and cranial sutures) and sex (through non-metric features of the cranium and pelvis) can establish whether interment at Rameț was limited by aspects of identity like age and sex.

RO2 – To investigate the intersection of social and bioarchaeological inequalities: Recent osteoarchaeological research has emphasized that social inequalities can lead to materialization of biological inequalities as a result of structurally violent processes such as colonization, slavery or rigid class systems^{4,5}. Most of this research has focused on states and empires. As a result, biological implications of significant social inequalities are still poorly understood in societies without large-scale infrastructural and institutional frameworks. Comparing osteological (e.g. age, sex) and material culture evidence (e.g. grave goods, mortuary treatment) of identity at Rameț to carbon and nitrogen analysis of diet, paleopathological data on physiological stress, infectious disease and labour burdens will help us to understand how and when emerging social inequalities were institutionalized and materialized in human bodies.

RO3 – To reconstruct community social interactions: Previous research has demonstrated the high potential of strontium and oxygen analysis of mobility in Transylvania⁶. This research is particularly important for the Apuseni region, where unanswered questions about the influence of non-local groups during the EBA remain. In particular, there are ongoing debates concerning the Yamnaya, a group that began moving into the Carpathian Basin from the Eurasian steppe during the Late Copper Age (circa 2800-2700 BC)⁷. Strontium and oxygen isotope analysis has been used successfully to help identify the extent of Yamnaya influence in other regions⁸. Here, isotopic analysis of mobility, combined with material culture studies of grave goods, mortuary treatment and tomb form has the potential to identify whether Yamnaya groups were moving into the Apuseni mountains, or whether indigenous Soimuș groups adopting Yamnaya mortuary practices as a strategy for forging links to metal resources in the mountains.

Originality and innovative aspects of the research program: This research program weaves together traditional osteoarchaeological analyses of human skeletal remains with cutting edge isotopic analyses to produce a more holistic understanding of life in the Early Bronze Age. MARBAL is unique in that it combines quantitative approaches to stable isotope analysis with a qualitative osteobiographical approach to the lives of individuals in the past. Such an approach is of particular utility in Romania, where little osteoarchaeological work has been conducted. As such, the results of the MARBAL project will provide new insight into the trajectory of the Bronze Age in this region, shifting the focus of analysis from settlements and material culture to the prehistoric people themselves.

1.2 Quality and appropriateness of the training and of the two way transfer of knowledge between the researcher and the host: The University of Cambridge offers the best opportunity for Dr Beck to acquire the new knowledge necessary for both MARBAL and career enhancement. At the same time, the University and Cambridge archaeology will benefit greatly from her presence and experience.

³ Holt, E. (ed.) (Forthcoming) *Water and Power in Past Societies*. SUNY Press.

⁴ Klaus, H. D. (2012). The bioarchaeology of structural violence: A theoretical model and a case study. In D. Martin (Ed.) *The Bioarchaeology of Violence*. (pp. 29-62). Gainesville, FL: University Press of Florida.

⁵ Robbins Schug, G., Blevins, K. E., Cox, B., Gray, K., and Mushrif-Tripathy, V. (2013). Infection, disease, and biosocial processes at the end of the Indus civilization. *PLoS ONE*, 8(12), 1-20.

⁶ Gerling, C., & Ciugudean, H. (2013). Insights into the Transylvanian Early Bronze Age using strontium and oxygen isotope analyses: A pilot study. In V. Heyd, G. Kulcsár & V. Szeverényi (Eds.), *Transitions to the Bronze Age: Interregional Interaction and Socio-Cultural Change in the Third Millennium BC Carpathian Basin and Neighbouring Regions*. (pp. 181-202). Budapest: Archaeolingua.

⁷ Ciugudean, H. (1996). *Epoca Timpurie a Bronzului în Centrul și Sud-Vestul Transilvaniei*. Bucharest: Ministerul Invatamantului.

⁸ Gerling, C., Heyd, V., Pike, A., Bánffy, E., Dani, J., Köhler, K., Kulcsár, G., Kaiser, E., & Schier, W. (2012). Identifying kurgan graves in eastern Hungary: A burial mound in light of strontium and oxygen isotope analysis. In J. Burger, E. Kaiser & W. Schier (Eds.), *Population dynamics in prehistory and early history: new approaches using stable isotopes and genetics*. (pp. 165-176). Boston: De Gruyter.

New knowledge gained by the experienced researcher: The Training programme and Objectives (TOs) comprise:

TO1 – Intellectual training in osteobiographical approaches to human skeletal remains: Dr Beck's postgraduate work has focused on quantitative approaches to human skeletal remains, but she has no experience with osteobiographical approaches. Professor Robb is a world leader in osteobiographical approaches, which use rigorous data drawn from human skeletal remains to construct narrative trajectories of the lives of prehistoric individuals and present a valuable addition to any exploration of community and individual identity. Professor Robb's supervision will provide much-needed theoretical grounding in osteobiography. This new theoretical training will also be bolstered by collaboration with The McDonald Institute Material Culture and the Body Project, a working group which focuses on materialization of Bronze Age communities and conceptualization of the body by a range of societies. It will help Dr Beck develop more nuanced theoretical approaches to the analysis of burials in EBA Europe.

TO2 – Training in analytical archaeological science: Dr Beck has previously collaborated with researchers at the University of Tübingen to analyse isotopes relevant to prehistoric diet and patterns of mobility. However, she lacks training in preparing and processing such samples, a skill which will be a significant asset in her future work. At the McDonald Institute, Dr Beck will work with Drs Tamsin O'Connell in the Dorothy Garrod Isotope and Palaeodiet Laboratory at the McDonald Institute for Archaeological Research, Cambridge, to develop skills in selecting bioarchaeological samples, extracting collagen for analysis and using a mass spectrometer. Training will be based on graduate courses in isotope analyses, mentorship and individual training from the aforementioned academics, plus practical training while processing lab samples from the MARBAL project. Acquisition of these skills is an important objective: it will provide a valuable toolkit for assessing diet and mobility in human skeletal remains. Dr Beck will supplement her existing osteoarchaeological skills through in-depth training in burial taphonomy and funerary ritual. Professor Robb has an extensive background of research on funerary taphonomy^{9,10}, and is currently supervising one PhD student and one Marie Curie fellow focused on this topic. This field is much better developed in Europe than in the U.S.A, and will complement Dr Beck's existing focus on quantitative approaches to mortuary practices in prehistory.

TO3 – Academic development: Transferable skills training will help Dr Beck develop her academic profile, whilst also facilitating the transfer to the host institution of her existing specialist knowledge and experience, principally through active participation in seminars/lectures/conferences and outreach events, in student supervision and training, in lecturing and in lasting networks of academic contacts and collaborations. Her transferable skills to improve career potential in the academic world, including Europe, comprise i) **exposure to European academic institutions and networks** that will enable Dr Beck to make new professional connections within the field of archaeology that will support her continuing research in Europe throughout her career; ii) **research project management**, including finance, logistics, risk management and IP issues, to familiarise her with procedures for supervising large research teams; this will be achieved through advice from the highly experienced McDonald Institute research support staff, the School funding team and the University's central Research Operations Office; iii) **increasing her potential to secure the large-scale (European and international) funding** necessary for major research projects and to establish wide international networks investigating past and present cultural change; iv) **improving other professional skills** necessary for both academic and non-academic jobs: teaching and supervising at a top-ranking academic institution, and presenting her work at public engagement and outreach events will improve her capacity to explain complex concepts and issues to the public and specialists. In addition, Dr Beck will attend seminars and discussions on issues of gender balance in research. Cambridge University was awarded an Athena SWAN Silver Award 2014, which recognizes its commitment and intensive activity in supporting and promoting women at all levels. She will be expected to undertake the Equality and Diversity training provided by the University and to attend as many of the SWAN events as possible as part of her additional and transferable skills training.

Transfer of knowledge to the host institution: Dr Beck brings her expert skills in osteoarchaeology, particularly the study of fragmentary and commingled remains, to Cambridge. This will widen the osteological research base in Cambridge significantly at a time when osteoarchaeological research is growing apace. She will complement existing expertise in mortuary archaeology and isotopic analyses, and help to create a kernel of excellence from which Cambridge and European archaeology will benefit. She will help Cambridge expand in statistics and quantitative techniques. Cambridge has just hired Enrico Crema as a lecturer in quantitative methods. However, there are currently no researchers bridging quantitative methods and osteoarchaeological and mortuary approaches, and Dr Beck's strong record of research in this area will make a unique contribution to the growing quantitative focus at Cambridge. She will offer graduate and undergraduate seminars on analysis of commingled human remains and dental anthropological

⁹ Knüsel, C., and J. Robb (In Press). Funerary taphonomy: An overview of goals and methods. *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports*, available online 31 May 2016.

¹⁰ Robb, J. (In Press). What can we really say about skeletal part representation, MNI and funerary ritual? A simulation approach. *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports*, available online 26 May 2016.

approaches (iv above), as preparation for fieldwork or research projects involving fragmentary skeletal remains. She will also develop collaborative seminars on quantitative methods in human bone work with the Wellcome-funded project “After the Plague,” working to develop topics with other researchers at Cambridge interested in mortuary archaeology and osteoarchaeology. Her knowledge of human skeletal analysis, in particular her experience with skeletal populations from Iberia and Romania, will supplement existing expertise at the McDonald Institute and will serve as a valuable resource for ongoing projects of Professor Robb (Italy; UK – St John’s College Cambridge medieval cemetery), Dr Miracle (Croatia, including a recently awarded H2020 Twinning project), the Cambridge Archaeological Unit (a spin-off professional archaeological unit) and others working across Europe. She will bring her networks of contacts and thereby facilitate further collaborative initiatives between these, the University and Europe. She will give seminars, e.g. McDonald lunchtime seminars, Material Culture and the Body Group and Garrod series. She already writes a blog named Bone Broke¹¹ which is a successful platform for education outreach that has been cited in a peer-reviewed publication, viewed over 150,000 times, and used as a teaching resource at 12 different institutions: through this she will continue to inform the public about the cutting-edge bioarchaeological research conducted during the MARBAL project. Dr Beck’s outreach will therefore serve as a model for ongoing public communication initiatives at the McDonald Institute. With research interests focused almost entirely on European archaeology, Dr Beck’s ambition is squarely focused on a career in European Science. Her contributions to the transfer of knowledge will thus include (1) Bringing a non-European researcher able to provide an advanced methodology to this field for the betterment of European heritage; (2) The potential to create long term collaborations and mutually beneficial co-operation between Europe and the Third Country (USA); strengthen collaboration between European researchers and USA; (3) Transfer of knowledge between universities of different countries (ERA and Third Country of origin), which will lead to widening of competencies of all staff and hence will be an essential for the development of science; (4) The transfer of knowledge will go two ways: Dr Beck will present seminars and will engage graduate students in Cambridge and at several national and international events. Through previous work Dr Beck is well-positioned to share technical information and assist both experienced researchers and students alike.

1.3 Quality of the supervision and of the integration in the team/institution

Qualifications and experience of the supervisor: Professor John Robb (BA – University of Chicago (1983), MA (1989) and PhD (1995) in anthropological archaeology, University of Michigan) is Professor in European Prehistory and Director of the Material Culture Laboratory at the University of Cambridge. His research focuses on European and Mediterranean prehistory, particularly Neolithic and Bronze Age with interests in cultural life, symbolism and historic processes. He is an acknowledged authority and expert in archaeological and anthropological theory, particularly agency theory, material culture, gender and body and scales of analysis/long term change, with an interest in specific topics highly relevant to MARBAL which include skeletal analysis, particularly signs of activity, funerary ritual and taphonomy, and extensions of social biography after death. He led the major Cambridge based ‘Body Project’ funded by a Leverhulme Trust Programme Grant and is the PI of a recently awarded Wellcome Trust Grant (£1.3M) exploring the effects of major health events on the people of medieval Cambridge through both osteoarchaeological and bioarchaeological analysis. He is also involved in several international collaborations and is a very active member of the Cambridge teaching staff. He teaches European Prehistory and Archaeological Theory and co-coordinates the MPhil module on Material Culture. He supervises PhD theses on a wide range of topics and has already hosted six Marie Curie Fellows, four current and two who have recently progressed to full-time permanent academic positions at high-ranking European universities. He is the Editor of the *Cambridge Archaeological Journal* and has published >50 papers in major international peer-reviewed journals as well as 8 books on agency theory and its application in archaeological and anthropological studies. See representative examples of publications in B5.

Hosting arrangements: Dr Beck will become a member of the McDonald Institute for Archaeological Research, with all facilities necessary for successful completion of the proposed research and training (see B3.3 & B5). The Institute is a world-ranking institution in archaeological research, recognised as one of the best international multidisciplinary archaeological host institutions for post-doctoral researchers at all levels and is renowned for nurturing future leaders in the field. Dr Beck can rely on a highly experienced research administration team to support her on arrival, during integration in Cambridge and throughout the duration of the project. The team will offer assistance to resolve problems of any kind and offer general information about accommodation, registration, facilities access etc. Central University academic, administrative and social networks and also help international researchers by ensuring smooth personal integration and productive research (e.g. The Newcomers and Visitors’ Society). PdOC (the Postdocs Cambridge Society) represents postdoctoral researchers from all faculties, schools and departments in Cambridge and provides information and support, facilitating communication and networking activities. As host and supervisor Professor Robb will oversee both project development and training – particularly in osteobiographical theory. He will

¹¹ www.bonebroke.org

welcome Dr Beck to the working group on Material Culture and the Body where existing members already explore themes in line with the objectives of MARBAL, e.g. the construction of social identities through material culture and mortuary treatment. In addition to the supervisor, whom she will meet formally on a weekly basis at the start of the project but later each month, Dr Beck will have the career mentoring of Dr Tamsin O’Connell, who will introduce her to the analysis of isotopes in human skeletal remains at the Dorothy Garrod Isotope and Palaeodiet Laboratory. There are a number of other researchers whose specialities overlap with Dr Beck’s research interest who will be able to provide important guidance and mentorship, including Professor Marie Louise Sørensen, who focuses on Bronze Age central and Eastern Europe, Dr Susan Hakenbeck, who conducts archaeological stable isotope analysis, and Dr Enrico Crema, a lecturer in quantitative methods. Dr Beck will also be able to join the community of researchers who focus on human bones in the Division of Biological Anthropology, both offering and receiving additional knowledge and expertise. On arrival in Cambridge Dr Beck will avail herself of the transferable skills programs (See TO3) offered by the University’s Personal and Professional Development service, the Cambridge University Careers Service and the McDonald Institute, the latter aimed specifically at the archaeological workplace. Weekly workshops deal with skills such as CV and research grant proposal writing, publication strategies (books, international high calibre peer-review journals, DTP and online publishing), presentation and teaching techniques, and organising successful fieldwork and student field trips. They are hosted for postdoctoral fellows and graduate students, ensuring that they receive the best possible preparation for competing on the international job market both in and outside academia. The ER will also attend the relevant weekly seminars and international workshops frequently held at the Institute, hosted by other laboratories and research clusters. She will give one talk per year as part of the McDonald Seminar series and make other presentations to specific disciplinary groups. The University also encourages scholars to attend seminars in all departments so she will therefore be able to join discussions in other relevant disciplines and integrate fully into the wider academic community. She will be able to apply for a College Research Associateship (unique to Oxbridge), further increasing potential intergenerational and interdisciplinary integration as she meets scholars from other disciplines within a social and academic setting.

1.4 Capacity of the researcher to reach or re-enforce a position of professional maturity/independence

Dr Beck’s drive to further develop her professional career in order to secure a position of maturity is demonstrated by her academic record (section B4). During her PhD, she published multiple papers on the development of new osteological methodologies and theoretical approaches to analysing human skeletal remains. This research required both independent and group data collection on national and international projects, and was partially funded by a highly competitive U.S. National Science Foundation Doctoral Dissertation Improvement Grant. These professional accomplishments, achieved at a very early stage in her academic career, demonstrate her ability to conduct collaborative international research, secure external funding and publish her research in top-tier academic journals. Dr Beck has also shown significant evidence of her commitment to public dissemination of research, including her successful education outreach blog *Bone Broke*, her position as a Science Communication Fellow in the National Science Foundation Portal-to-the-Public Program and her dedication to giving public talks and lectures about archaeology and anthropology (see B4). Her ability to embrace new knowledge and opportunities rapidly is proven by her success developing and executing a bioarchaeological research project in Spain, and collaborating on field projects, data collection and research across the world, including Portugal, Illinois, Arizona and Sudan. MARBAL integrates her significant experience in analysis of human skeletal remains with new theoretical approaches and establishment of a long-term European field project. Overall, her track record demonstrates capacity and potential to become an excellent established Researcher with high likelihood of achieving her professional goal of securing a tenure-track position within a top-flight European academic institution.

2. IMPACT

2.1 Enhancing the potential and future career prospects of the researcher

Impact of planned research and training on career prospects of experienced researcher: The methodological training, academic mentorship and networking opportunities received by Dr Beck in Cambridge will greatly increase her future employment prospects in both the European and global academic community. Conducting research at an internationally-recognized and top-tier institution will result in considerable intellectual and personal development.

Acquisition of new competencies: Supervision by Professor Robb in ‘osteobiography’ and additional mentorship by other Cambridge faculty, exposure to new theoretical perspectives and improvement of her existing skills base will ensure continuing intellectual growth as a scholar. This new combination of methodological and theoretical skills provides the foundation for archaeological analysis of embodied social inequalities, one of the core themes of MARBAL which she will be able to develop into even greater initiatives on completion of the project. The opportunity for guided practice in carbon, nitrogen, strontium and oxygen analysis that Dr Beck will receive will significantly expand her methodological skillset and provide transferable skills that will be invaluable in her future career. The skills that Dr Beck will develop in analytical archaeological science will enable her to train future students

in these methods and extend her capabilities in academic and non-academic fields and job markets, thereby serving her throughout her future research career.

Developing a collaborative European research network, with colleagues in Cambridge and elsewhere, will also help ensure Dr Beck's success in continuing to conduct cutting-edge osteoarchaeological research in Europe. Her research in Romania will entail work with local collaborators and institutions with the aim of securing local participation in the heritage preservation for the benefit of local communities and future research. Working with local archaeologists and communities will provide Dr Beck with the chance to engage in collaborative community archaeology, a skill-set becoming increasingly important when applying for external funding and jobs in archaeology. Because her past research has been focused on museum collections, this is a skill set which she has not yet been able to obtain.

2.2 Quality of the proposed measures to exploit and disseminate the action results

Results of MARBAL will be disseminated through various media, including presentations at academic conferences, the organization of conference sessions, peer-reviewed journal articles and Dr Beck's existing blog, as outlined below:

1) Scientific presentations at international conferences, including the **EAA** (*European Association of Archaeologists*) in Barcelona, Spain, September 5-9, 2018 the **AAPA** (*American Association of Physical Anthropologists*), in Cleveland, U.S.A, March 26-30, 2019, the **SAA** (*Society for American Archaeology*) in Albuquerque, New Mexico., U.S.A, April 10-14, 2019, and more specialized conferences focused on the analysis of human skeletal remains such as **BABAO** (*British Association for Biological Anthropology and Osteoarchaeology*) – the dates and location for BABAO 2019 are as yet undetermined, but the conference usually takes place in September; **2) The organization of an invited session at an international conference** (EAA 2018), focused on bringing together European archaeologists conducting research on the emergence of inequality across EBA Europe, particularly those integrating interdisciplinary datasets; **3) Articles in major international peer-reviewed journals with open-access policy** e.g. *Antiquity*, the *Journal of Archaeological Science* and the *American Journal of Physical Anthropology*. **4) Submission of an edited volume to Oxford University Press on social inequality in Bronze Age Europe**, developed from the invited conference session described as item 2; **5) Dissemination of results on the MARBAL project website**. This website will be linked to Dr Beck's existing blog *Bone Broke*, which will have the added benefit of publicizing the results to a non-specialist audience online. **6) Dissemination of results through a workshop at Cambridge**: Dr Beck will organize a workshop at Cambridge focused on quantitative approaches to osteoarchaeological remains, and the contributions that such approaches can make to archaeological understandings of mortuary practices in prehistory. At the Cambridge workshop, Dr Beck will discuss her research results with other experts in the field and identify new directions for quantitative research, expanding her networks of European academic contacts. **7) A Data Management Plan (DMP) will be finalised before the end of month 3**: before embarking on fieldwork in Romania Dr Beck will outline an agreement with all collaborators that specifies each participant's role, budgetary responsibilities and contribution to future authorship and publications. Permits for site survey, site excavation and export of human remains will be applied for through the Romanian Archaeology Commission in advance of each season of fieldwork. Upon academic publication, Dr Beck's data will be published under a Creative Commons license in her name, and her research results will be disseminated across a number of open-access platforms. This dissemination will help to provide easy open access to information to the national Romanian population, a form of communication rarely undertaken in Romania due to cost and logistical issues. This will help to increase local knowledge of the prehistory and heritage of the region of study. Author-Accepted-Manuscripts will be placed on the Cambridge University open-access website (<https://www.openaccess.cam.ac.uk>). All raw data generated during the EF will be made available on the MARBAL project website and placed on the University's data repository website (<http://www.data.cam.ac.uk/repository>). Research data management will be outlined in a DMP, and carried out under WP1. No commercial exploitation or patents are predicted. Finally, all outputs will prominently include acknowledgement of the support of the MSCA and H2020, increasing the profile of EU Excellence in Science and Research.

2.3 Quality of the proposed measures to communicate the action activities to different target audiences

Dr. Beck has a demonstrated commitment to science communication and outreach, and will continue to pursue public dissemination of her results while in Cambridge. She will act as an MSCA Ambassador, promoting scientific research and raising awareness of the fields of archaeology, anthropology and the scientific study of human skeletal remains. As a result, MARBAL will contribute to the dissemination of archaeological knowledge and results to the general public. This communication and public engagement strategy will be achieved through a two-pronged approach:

1) Public outreach: Dr Beck already has significant experience in public science outreach, having participated in four public 'Archaeology Days' and four 'Behind the Scenes Days' at the Ruthven Museum of Natural History (RMNH) in Ann Arbor, Michigan. She has also attended two National Science Foundation 'Portal to the Public' workshops on science outreach and developed a hands-on osteology activity for young children, which she presented at a public 'Discovery Day' and 'Scientist Spotlight' at the RMNH. She will build on this strong pre-existing skill set to participate in a variety of outreach activities at Cambridge, including the *Science Festival*

(<http://www.sciencefestival.cam.ac.uk/>), the *Festival of Ideas*, (<http://www.festivalofideas.cam.ac.uk/>), *Pint of Science* (<https://pintofscience.co.uk/city/cambridge>) and the McDonald Institute Prehistory Day (<http://www.mcdonald.cam.ac.uk/events-all/prehistory-day>). She will co-plan one of the Cambridge MSCA Ambassador Events to publicize the results of Fellows’ research and the MSC programme to potential future applicants and demonstrate the value of European and international science. Dr Beck has given a wide range of public lectures in her career thus far, within academic departments, disciplinary work groups, ‘brown bag’ lunch series, and local archaeological societies (B4), and she will continue to pursue such opportunities for outreach in these activities in both the UK and Romania in order to publicize the research she achieves while holding the fellowship. Finally, Dr Beck will also utilize the resources available at the Cambridge University Press Office to generate local interest in and media coverage of her work. She plans to publicize her research in venues such as Radiolab (www.radiolab.org) and The Naked Scientists (www.thenakedscientist.com) podcast series, which is broadcast on BBC and ABC, one of the top ten downloaded science podcasts in the world. Dr Beck will also share her research using the recently launched Ofcom-licensed TV channel for Cambridge <http://www.cambridge-tv.co.uk/> (Freeview channel 8, Virgin Media and online), which highlights the best in Cambridge arts, science, business and culture for bright, curious viewers locally and around the world, and includes a weekly science show ‘Elemental Ideas’ as well as culture and arts shows, providing a chance to share work with a wide audience.

2) A MARBAL website linked to existing outreach blog: By developing a MARBAL project website linked to her existing popular blog, *Bone Broke*, Dr Beck will disseminate research results to an ever-expanding public audience with a demonstrated interest in archaeology and human osteology. The MARBAL website will have both field and lab components, providing the general public with a guide to how archaeological data are collected and analysed, from excavation to publication. She will also use social media such as Facebook and Twitter to continue generating new interest in the results of her research, and publicize her own research and the research of her MSCA peers on dedicated research blogging sites (e.g. <http://www.researchblogging.org/>).

3. QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY OF THE IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 Coherence and effectiveness of the work plan

Gantt Chart

MARBAL will take place over a 24-month period with an anticipated start date of 01 October 2017. Time will be divided between Cambridge, where lab facilities and resources will support the achievement of research and training objectives, and two field seasons in Romania for excavation and data collection (June – August 2018 and May – June 2019). MARBAL will be undertaken in conjunction with the Rameț archaeological project, which will begin field excavations in June, July, and August 2017, prior to the start of the MARBAL project itself. This initial field season of the Rameț archaeological project will allow the team to excavate one tomb (C) and set up the field site for future seasons. The second field season will take place from June – August 2018, and excavate two tombs (A, B). Data collection for the MARBAL project will begin during this second season of the Rameț archaeological project, and at the end of August 2018 Dr Beck will export the human skeletal remains recovered from tombs A, B, and C for analysis at the McDonald Institute for Archaeological Research. The third field season of the Rameț archaeological project will taken place in May and June 2019, and will coincide with the second phase of data collection for the MARBAL project, when a final targeted sample of human skeletal remains will be exported to Cambridge for isotopic analysis in July, August, and September 2019. The results of this analysis will mark the conclusion of the MARBAL project. Romanian permits and import licenses are available from the National Archaeology Commission. Collaborators Colin Quinn and Horia Ciugudean from the Rameț archaeological project are both members of the Romanian National Registry of Archaeologists (*Registrul Arheologilor*) and are thus able to apply for permits, and the

human skeletal remains will be imported to the United Kingdom under a governmental permit from the Department of Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA). DEFRA permits cannot be applied for more than 3 months in advance. However, the procedure is straightforward and the Host Organisation has a long track record of successful DEFRA permit applications. Although no formal ethical approval is necessary for work on archaeological human material from across the EU, either in Romania or in the UK, all project materials will be handled in accordance with Departmental practice which follows national and international guidelines: the ER will ensure that human skeletal remains are always treated with dignity, sensitivity and respect and will comply with the code of ethics set out by the British Association for Biological Anthropology and Osteoarchaeology and the Society for American Archaeology. The specific Work Packages (WP), associated objectives, deliverables (D), milestones (M), and deadlines are presented in the Gant Chart below, and further outlined in sections A and B which follow:

A) Training Through Research and Project Implementation

WP1: Logistics, set up, and monitoring. During October 2017 (month 1) Dr Beck will arrive in Cambridge, undertake a first face-to-face meeting with Professor Robb to finalize a research schedule and career development plan, meet with Dr O’Connell to finalize isotopic training schedule and receive an introduction to the Dorothy Garrod Laboratory for Isotopic Analysis. During this set-up phase, she will schedule meetings with Prof Robb to receive input on the proposed research design and to create a research schedule document (D1.1), and career development plan (D1.2). These meetings will allow for the evaluation of progress and the discussion of any additional training required and any adjustments to research plan during and after data collection. Prior to leaving for the first phase of data collection, the ER will work with Professor Robb in order to develop a Data Management Plan (D1.3). Supervisor monitoring and input will continue during the data collection phases of MARBAL. During the first and second seasons of data collection (months 9-11; 20-21), Dr Beck will Skype with Prof Robb and Dr O’Connell once each month, to continue to incorporate their input into the data collection plan in the field. A mid-term report will be developed in month 12, after the first season of data collection. Deliverables: D1.1: research schedule document; D1.2: career development plan; D1.3 Data Management Plan; D1.4 Mid-term report.

WP2: Training in osteobiography and funerary taphonomy (months 1-8, 13-19). Directly after her arrival in Cambridge, Dr Beck will meet with Professor Robb to assemble a reading list pertinent to osteobiographical theory and funerary taphonomy. Dr Beck and Professor Robb will then meet on a monthly basis while she is in Cambridge to discuss how to apply osteobiographical theory and funerary taphonomy to the MARBAL project in order to produce deeper understandings of social biography after death in the Bronze Age world. This training will be supplemented through participation in the McDonald Institute’s Material Culture and the Body Project. Deliverables consist of: D2.1 Initial meeting with Professor Robb to chart a course for study, while milestones include Dr Beck presenting her research to the Material Culture and the Body group (M2.1) and submitting an article to *Antiquity* focused on the use of osteobiographical approaches to Late Prehistoric Europe (M2.2).

WP3: Receive training, process and interpret stable isotope results (months 1-8, 12-19, 22-24). Phase I Training: Fundamentals of stable isotope analysis: Attendance at MPhil isotopic analyses courses (3rd October-1st December 2017), including training in the theory, method, and practice of stable isotope analysis through hands-on experience in the Dorothy Garrod Laboratory. **Phase II Training: Selection, treatment, and preparation of samples:** The researcher will gain practical experience in selecting and analysing samples for carbon (C), nitrogen (N), and strontium (Sr), working with Dr O’Connell in the Dorothy Garrod Laboratory. During Phase II training, Dr O’Connell will mentor Dr Beck in her isotopic analysis of the human remains imported from Romania after the first season of MARBAL data collection in summer 2018. The number of samples analysed will be determined after each season of excavation, when a Minimum Number of Individuals can be estimated for the excavated burials. Deliverables include: D3.1: Sample selection and preparation for materials from the first season of MARBAL data collection; D3.2: Analysis and interpretation of C, N and Sr isotopes from first season of MARBAL data collection; D3.3: Sample selection and preparation for materials from second season of MARBAL data collection; D3.4: Analysis and interpretation of C, N and Sr isotopes from the second season of MARBAL data collection.

WP4: Collection of archaeological samples in Romania (month 9-11, 20-21). The first season of data collection for the MARBAL project will coincide with the second field season of the Rameț archaeological project, and human remains will be exported for study at Cambridge to coincide with Dr Beck’s return to Cambridge in September 2018. During summer 2018, the ER will join the Rameț archaeological project in the excavation of tomb C, and prepare the human remains from tombs A, B, and C for export to Cambridge for analysis. During the summer 2019 field season, the ER will join the Rameț archaeological project in the excavation of Tomb D, and prepare the human remains from this locale for export to Cambridge for analysis during July – September 2019. Deliverables: D2.1: Export of materials from the first season MARBAL data collection, D2.2: Export of materials from the second season of MARBAL data collection.

WP5: Analysis of remains from Rameț-Gugului (month 1-3, 13-15). Analysis of the human remains from Rameț is key to achieving the research objectives of the MARBAL project (section 1.1). There are three necessary steps for

analysis: 1) cleaning the remains, 2) sorting the remains in the event of commingling, and 3) conducting a thorough osteological and bioarchaeological analysis that assesses age, sex, health, and disease of the excavated individuals. Milestones: M5.1 Complete bioarchaeological analysis of individuals from first season of MARBAL data collection; M5.2 Complete bioarchaeological analysis of smaller sample of remains from second season of MARBAL data collection.

B) Additional Activities to further develop and widen the ER's general skills and competencies:

WP6: Engagement with and dissemination to academic and non-academic communities (month 1-24). Dr Beck will collaborate with Cambridge Archaeology's Outreach and Communications Administrator and the Public Engagement Team of the University of Cambridge, and use a variety of media to address the general public and other academics, with a particular emphasis on outreach for non-specialists. Deliverables include: D6.1 Project website (month 1). This will be updated frequently until the completion of the project. D6.2 Project page on Facebook (month 1). This will be updated frequently until the completion of the project. D6.3 Dr Beck will participate in the McDonald Institute *Prehistory Day* during the second year that she holds the MSCA EF (**month 12**), presenting an interactive station on the analysis of bones from archaeological contexts. D6.4 She will also participate in the Cambridge *Festival of Ideas* (**month 12**). D6.5 At Cambridge, Dr Beck will host a workshop on quantitative approaches to human remains that disseminates the results of the MARBAL project and integrates her training in stable isotope analysis, osteobiography, and funerary taphonomy. D6.6 Dr Beck will present a poster at the AAPA meetings in Cleveland, Ohio in March 2019, describing the results of the MARBAL strontium analysis. D6.7 Dr Beck will give a podium presentation at the Society for American Archaeology meetings in Albuquerque, New Mexico in April 2019, describing the results from the first season of the MARBAL project analysis. D6.8 Dr Beck will present a poster at the BABAO meetings in September 2019, describing the results from the MARBAL analysis of carbon and nitrogen isotopes. A major milestone related to WP6 (M6.1) will occur when the ER organizes a session at the European Association of Archaeologists meetings in Barcelona, Spain, in 2018 that brings together European archaeologists conducting research on the emergence of inequality across EBA Europe while integrating interdisciplinary datasets.

3.2. Appropriateness of the allocation of tasks and resources

The tasks and resources outlined in Section 3.1 are essential to fulfilling the MARBAL research objectives. The proposed schedule lays out a clear timeline for Dr Beck to receive training in osteobiography and stable isotopic analysis, to conduct fieldwork in Romania and osteoarchaeological analysis of the human skeletal remains from MARBAL, and to disseminate the results of her research. The 24-month project will begin on 1 October 2017 in order to match the University of Cambridge academic year. In this way the ER can join formal advanced classes as well as receive individual training and undertake the training-through-research so that all aspects of the relevant science and skills are covered in an appropriate manner. The schedule includes both intensive lab-based training and 8 months of analysis (which includes training-through research) as well as dissemination. The plans help to ensure feasibility and credibility of the project aims and expected outcomes. The MSCA research and training allowance is currently €19,200. This sum will allow for two data collection visits to Romania in June-August 2018 and May-June 2019 calculated in total at €11,389: two round trip National Express bus fares between Cambridge and London Heathrow = €150; two flights between London Heathrow and Budapest = €488; rental car fee = €1,060/month x 5 months = €5,300; petrol = €66/week x 20 weeks = €1,320; room and board in Alba Iulia, Romania = €27/day x 153 = €4131. It will also enable the coverage of participation in four conferences in total, calculated at €5000 [per conference on average €600 airfare; €80 per day accommodation x 5 days = €400; conference fee = €250]. The remaining resources will be used to cover the costs of consumables involved in the isotope analysis, supplemented where necessary by funding from the *D.M. McDonald Grants and Awards Fund* for which the ER will be entitled to apply. The ER will monitor and manage finances through receiving regular monthly reports from the Faculty Finance Officer, and will also have access to the 'Research Expenditure Application' that is updated on a daily basis to assess spending.

Quality and progress monitoring will be assured by the monthly meetings with the supervisor and the mentor respectively. The time allocation described is appropriate as it will allow the ER to complete tasks on schedule, and will reduce the risks of over-running individual WPs and tasks.

3.3 Appropriateness of the management structure and procedures, including risk management

Organization and management structure: Coordination of research and financial activities will be undertaken jointly by Dr Beck and Professor Robb, with input from the Host as appropriate (**WP1** above). Initially Dr Beck will have weekly meetings with Professor Robb to monitor progress and discuss the project, including finances, where appropriate drawing on formal written reports (**D1.1 & D1.4**), the Career Development Plan agreed with the Mentor (**D1.3**) and the Data Management Plans (**D1.2**) to keep the Fellowship on track in terms of deliverables and milestones. Professor Robb's unparalleled capacity as a mentor is demonstrated by the success of the previous MSCA EFs he has supervised. The extensive experience of the McDonald Institute in managing EU funding guarantees that the project is managed financially according to the EC's regulations and that the Fellow is regularly updated on project finances. From month 2 meetings with Professor Robb will be monthly unless otherwise deemed necessary.

Risk mitigation strategy: Overall the risks that endanger fulfilment of the proposed research are low. MARBAL collaborators Colin Quinn and Horia Ciugudean have previously conducted extensive field research in this region of Romania, and conducting a topographical survey of the site in October 2016 will enable MARBAL to apply for an excavation permit in May 2017, in advance of the first season of fieldwork. Potential risks endangering the research project objectives are (1) unforeseen environmental damage leading to destruction of the site; (2) time issues related to excavation. Regarding (1), there are a high number of alternate unexcavated cemeteries in the Apuseni mountain region, and a ‘back-up’ site (either Geoagiu de Sus – Cuciu or Ponor) will be selected during the summer 2016 season of the Ramet archaeological project. (2) If the tombs take longer to excavate than anticipated due to either an unexpectedly high volume of human remains or intricate stratigraphy, the MARBAL project will adjust its sampling strategy accordingly. Progress monitoring will occur via monthly progress meetings with the host scientists, and a number of deliverables and milestones. These measures allow efficient progress monitoring and adjustment of schedule if necessary.

3.4 Appropriateness of the institutional environment (infrastructure)

Main tasks and commitments of the beneficiary and all partner organizations: The McDonald Institute and University of Cambridge are fully committed to the MSCA Fellowship programme of H2020, as demonstrated by the number and range of FP7 and H2020 Fellows already hosted. Institute staff, including supervisor, mentor and colleagues, and administrative and finance staff, all affirm their full commitment and support for the research and training described. In return the ER will become fully involved in daily life at the Institute, contribute to the growing programme in quantitative methods and contribute to the expanding academic and outreach network by taking part in numerous activities. Evidence for institutional commitment includes: a) the employment of Dr Beck as a postdoctoral Fellow at the McDonald Institute, b) agreement to provide personalised training, c) the strong experience, thus interest, of both organization and supervisor in running similar projects and training research students including ECRs, d) long-term interests in Cambridge in the project’s specific sub-discipline.

The University of Cambridge is the Host Organisation/Beneficiary, providing a perfect fit between project, ER and environment/resources. The McDonald Institute is the most appropriate host scientific unit for MARBAL due to both the unparalleled intellectual environment of researchers working on topics pertinent to mortuary archaeology and European Late Prehistory as well as the research facilities available to receive practical training in stable isotopic analysis. The McDonald Institute, Division of Archaeology and closely linked Division of Biological Anthropology have a long tradition, supported by associated infrastructure and human resources, in attracting, training and/or supporting exceptional researchers and projects from across the world, and in leading developments in science and innovation as world-class centres for education and research. The Institute will provide office and laboratory space, along with access to the Haddon Library (devoted to Archaeology and Anthropology), which will act as an optimal environment for scholarly analysis and productivity that will ensure the success of the MARBAL project. As a member of the Institute, Dr Beck will also be able to apply for additional funding of c.£ 5000 from the *D.M. McDonald Grants and Awards Fund* to support her research and fieldwork and £1,000 towards the costs of conference/workshop organisation. The University provides free access to the University copyright Library and a full suite of online resources, the specialist Science Periodicals Library, the Computer Service and Laboratory, with a full suite of additional training available to researchers, and the Language Laboratory. The ER will have access to relevant facilities across the University, including

1) **Intellectual environment:** The McDonald Institute has a proven record of success hosting c.30 postdoctoral researchers each year, an academic community with which Dr Beck will network and collaborate. In addition to a strong archaeological science group (see below), there is a strong tradition of research on ‘Material Culture and the Body’, as evidenced by the Leverhulme Trust funded ‘*Changing Beliefs of the Human Body*’ project, headed by Professor Robb, which will provide Dr Beck with the opportunity to exchange ideas with researchers working on a number of pertinent theoretical topics (such as gender, identity, archaeological theory) in different regions, allowing for fruitful exchange of ideas and understanding.

2) **Research facilities:** Amongst the facilities and resources available to the archaeological science community in Cambridge, the Dorothy Garrod Laboratory for Isotopic Analysis contains a wide array of preparation and analytical equipment for the analysis of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $^{87/86}\text{Sr}$, including multiple mass spectrometers, and affiliated researchers are able to prepare strontium samples in the clean room facilities in the Department of Earth Sciences which is located next door to the McDonald Institute. These facilities will be key to Dr Beck’s training in archaeological analysis and program of research. The relationship between the two centres is an established one of great collaborative and cooperative benefit to each. It provides a model of multidisciplinary for the ER to observe in action and to take with her as she moves to the next, advanced stage of her career in a position of enhanced professional maturity in Science.

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B4. Curriculum Vitae of the Experienced Researcher

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Name: Dr. Jessica Beck

Date of birth: 11/10/1987

ACADEMIC POSITIONS

2016-2017: **Visiting Scholar**, University of Pittsburgh, USA, Center for Comparative Archaeology.

EDUCATION

2011-2016: **PhD in Anthropology**, University of Michigan, USA. Thesis: The Bioarchaeology of Mortuary Practice at Marroquíes Bajos, Spain.

2009-2011: **MA in Anthropology**, University of Michigan, USA.

2008-2009: **Diploma in Environment**, McGill University, Canada.

2005-2008: **BA, 1st Class Honours Anthropology, English Literature**, McGill University, Canada.

RESEARCH INTERESTS

Bioarchaeology, human osteology, emerging social complexity, commingled human remains, European prehistory, paleopathology, bioarchaeological approaches to social identity.

PUBLICATIONS (IR = In Review)

- IR Kinkopf, Katherine and Jess Beck. Bioarchaeological approaches to looting: A case study from Sudan. Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports, revisions resubmitted August 24, 2016.
- 2016 Quinn, Colin and Jess Beck. Essential tensions in mortuary contexts: Exploring inequality through bioarchaeology. Open Archaeology, Topical Issue in Bioarchaeology. 2:18-41.
- 2016 Beck, Jess. Minding the gaps: A methodological approach to inter-individual variability in skeletal completion. American Antiquity 81(4):148-156.
- 2015 Beck, Jess. Part of the family: Age, identity and burial in Copper Age Iberia. In Theoretical Approaches to Analysis and Interpretation of Commingled Human Remains. Edited by A. Osterholtz, pp. 47-73. Springer International: Cham.
- 2015 Beck, Jess, Ian Ostericher, Gregory Sollish and Jason De León. Animal scavenging and scattering and the implications for documenting the deaths of undocumented border crossers in the Sonoran Desert. Journal of Forensic Sciences 60: S11-S20.
- 2008 Beck, Jessica and Stephen Chrisomalis. Landscape archaeology, paganism, and the interpretation of megaliths. The Pomegranate: The International Journal of Pagan Studies 10(2): 142-162.

FELLOWSHIPS, RESEARCH GRANTS, AND SCHOLARSHIPS (Totaling c. 97,575 euros)

EXTERNAL RESEARCH GRANTS

- 2016: American Association of Physical Anthropologists William S. Pollitzer Student Travel Award (\$500).
- 2014: National Science Foundation Doctoral Dissertation Improvement Grant: “Social organization and mortuary practices at Marroquíes Bajos, Spain” (\$25,180).
- 2014: American Association of Physical Anthropologists William S. Pollitzer Student Travel Award (\$500).
- 2008: American Center of Oriental Research Jennifer C. Groot Fellowship (\$1,500).

INTERNAL RESEARCH GRANTS

- 2014: UMMAA Graduate Radiocarbon Years Before Present (\$1,425).
- 2014: Rackham International Research Award (\$6,000).
- 2014: Rackham Graduate Student Research Grant – Candidate (\$2,982).
- 2014-2016: International Institute Conference Travel Grants (\$900).
- 2013: James B. Griffin Scholarship Fund (\$3,000).
- 2012: Department of Anthropology Fellowships Committee Grant (\$1,719).
- 2012: Center for European Studies Summer Research Grant (\$1,004).
- 2012-2016: Rackham Conference Travel Grants (\$3,948).
- 2009: Rackham Graduate Student Research Grant – Pre-Candidate (\$1,500).
- 2009: Department of Anthropology Fieldwork Grant (\$1,400).

FELLOWSHIPS AND AWARDS

- 2016: Milford H. Wolpoff Graduate Student Writing Award (\$1,000).
 2015: Mary Malcomson Raphael Fellowship, Center for the Education of Women (\$17,176).
 2015: Department of Anthropology Block Grant Write-Up Fellowship (\$9,485).
 2015: Rackham Outstanding Graduate Student Instructor Award (\$1,000).
 2015: Sweetland Dissertation Writing Institute (\$3,000).
 2015: Rackham Humanities Research Fellowship (\$9,500).
 2015: Outstanding Teaching Award, Department of Anthropology (\$100).
 2012: Innovative Teaching Award, Department of Anthropology (\$100).
 2009-2012: LSA Regent's Fellowship, University of Michigan (\$16,000).

TEACHING EXPERIENCE

- 2016: **Instructor of Record (IR):** Inequality and the Body in Archaeology and Bioarchaeology, Graduate Seminar, University of Pittsburgh.
 2015: **IR:** The Science of Skeletons: Introduction to Bioarchaeology, University of Michigan.
 2014: **Graduate Student Instructor (GSI):** Nutrition & Human Evolution, University of Michigan.
 2013: **GSI:** Primate Social Behavior, University of Michigan.
 2013: **GSI:** Introduction to Biological Anthropology, University of Michigan.
 2012: **GSI:** Human Behavioral Ecology, University of Michigan.
 2011: **GSI:** Human Evolution, University of Michigan.
 2010: **GSI:** Human Evolution, University of Michigan.

CONFERENCE PRESENTATIONS (* = invited session)

- 2016, 09/ – Díaz-Zorita Bonilla, M., **J. Beck**, H. Bocherens, J. Escudero Carillo, M. Isabel Martínez Navarrete, J. Vicent, P. Díaz-del-Río. “Dental paleopathology, diet, and mobility at the Copper Age site of Marroquíes Bajos (Jaén, Spain).” European Association of Archaeologists, Biogeochemical Approaches to Archaeological Diet, Mobility and Disease Podium Session.
 2016, 04/15 – **Beck, J.** and M. Díaz-Zorita Bonilla. “Bodies in motion: Isotopic analyses of mobility and diet at Marroquíes Bajos, Spain.” American Association of Physical Anthropologists, Bioarchaeology Poster Session.
 *2016, 04/08 – **Beck, J.** “Mortuary multiplicity: Variability in mortuary treatment at a Late Prehistoric matrix village from Spain.” Society for American Archaeology, Buried, Burned, Bundled and Broken: Approaches to Co-Occurrence of Multiple Methods, Treatments and Styles of Burials Within Past Societies Podium Session.
 2015, 02/09 – Díaz-Zorita, M., **J. Beck**, J. Escudero, H. Bocherens, M. Martínez-Navarrete, J. Vicent, and P. Díaz-del-Río. “Testing the scale of human mobility at the third millennium BC mega-site of Marroquíes Bajos (Jaén, Spain) through 87Sr/86Sr and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ isotope analyses”. European Association of Archaeologists, (Re)writing the Past Using ‘Novel’ Scientific Techniques Podium Session.
 2015, 04/18 – **Beck, J.** “Commingled, communal and complex: reconstructing Iberian Copper Age mortuary practices.” Society for American Archaeology, Bioarchaeology and Mortuary Archaeology in Europe Podium Session.
 2015, 04/17 – Kinkopf, K. and **J. Beck**. “Bioarchaeological detection of looting: A case study from Sudan.” Society for American Archaeology, Global Studies in Bioarchaeology and Mortuary Archaeology Poster Session.
 2015, 03/26 – **Beck, J.** “A dental approach to salvage excavated and commingled burials.” American Association of Physical Anthropologists, Bioarchaeology Poster Session.
 *2015, 01/09 – Hall, K., A. Antoniou and **J. Beck**. “Etched in bone: The forensic taphonomy of undocumented migration.” Society for Historical Archaeology, Crossing Borders and Erasing Boundaries: An Overview of the First Five Years of the UMP Podium Session.
 2014, 04/26 – Hall, K., A. Antoniou, H. Stewart, **J. Beck** and J. De León. “Exploring the taphonomic processes that impact the remains of undocumented border crossers in the Sonoran Desert of Arizona.” Society for American Archaeology, Archaeology in the Modern World Poster Session.
 *2014, 04/24 – **Beck, J.** “Age, identity and burial in Copper Age Iberia.” Society for American Archaeology, Theoretical Approaches to Analysis and Interpretation of Commingled Human Remains Presentation Session.
 2014, 04/10 - **Beck, J.** “Intrasite variability in subadult burial during the Iberian Copper Age.” American Association of Physical Anthropologists, Bioarchaeology: Childhood, Population Dynamics and Cranial Change Poster Session.

- 2013, 04/05 – De León, J., **J. Beck**, G.Sollish and S.Yackhsaw. “Desert death, taphonomy, and the ethics of killing animals to understand what happens to the corpses of border crossers.” Society for American Archaeology, Violence, Place-Making and The Materiality of Border Crossing Poster Session.
- 2013, 03/11 – **Beck, J.** “Dental evidence of changes in female social status during the Middle to Late Woodland Transition.” American Association of Physical Anthropologists, Bioarchaeology: aDNA, Paleodemography, Status and Variation Poster Session.
- 2012, 04/18 – **Beck J.** “Diachronic change in avifaunal exploitation at four Late Pueblo village sites in southeastern New Mexico.” Society for American Archaeology, Zooarchaeology and Animal Use Poster Session.

CAMPUS, DEPARTMENTAL, AND PUBLIC TALKS

- 2016, 03/18 – How bioarchaeology can contribute to studies of mobility and movement in the past” – University of Michigan Collaborative Archaeology Workgroup Conference, Migration and mobility: Permanent and persistent movements of people.
- 2015, 11/09 – “Bare bones? Bioarchaeological approaches to prehistory.” Department of Anthropology, Four-Field Graduate Talks.
- 2015, 10/15 – “Bioarchaeological approaches to Copper Age complexity.” Kelsey Museum Field Archaeology Series on Thursday (FAST) Lecture Series.
- 2015, 10/01 – “Piecing together the puzzle: The bioarchaeology of early complex societies in Iberia.” University of Michigan Museum of Anthropology Brown Bag.
- 2015, 09/17 – “Skeleton keys: Using bioarchaeology to unlock the prehistoric past.” Michigan Archaeology Society, Huron Valley Chapter.
- 2013, 12/03 – “Bring out your dead: What bioarchaeology and mortuary practices can tell us about social organization and identity in Copper Age Iberia.” Department of Anthropology, Four-Field Graduate Talks.
- 2013, 11/21 – “Collective burials in Copper Age Iberia: Preliminary research at the site of Marroquíes Bajos, Jaén.” University of Michigan Museum of Anthropology Brown Bag.
- 2013, 03/23 – “Shifting skeletons: Osteological indicators of health during the Middle to Late Woodland transition in the lower Illinois River valley.” University of Michigan Four Field Anthropology Graduate Conference.
- 2012, 10/02 – “Death and burial in Copper Age Iberia.” Weiser Center for Europe and Eurasia, International Institute.
- 2009, 10/31 – “The potential for hybridization between Neanderthals and AMHs: A survey of biological parallels and the ecological potential for interbreeding in Europe.” University of Michigan Graduate Workshop on Archaeology and Material Culture.

SELECTED ARCHAEOLOGICAL FIELD AND LABORATORY EXPERIENCE

- 2013-2015: **Director**, Marroquíes Bajos Bioarchaeological Project, Jaen, Spain.
Bioarchaeological analysis of commingled and fragmentary remains of more than 200 individuals.
- 2012: **Field archaeologist**, Bolorés Mortuary Rockshelter. Directed by Katina Lillios, University of Iowa.
- 2011: **Crew chief**, Garden Creek Archaeology Project. Directed by Alice Wright, University of Michigan.
- 2010: **Field archaeologist**, Phosphorus Sampling and Survey on Visingsö. Directed by T.J. Chevral, University of Buffalo.
- 2010: **Field archaeologist**, Bolorés Mortuary Rockshelter. Directed by Katina Lillios, University of Iowa.
- 2009: **Field archaeologist**, Social Change and the Environment in Northern Prehistory, Directed by Andre Costopoulos, McGill University.
- 2009: **Field Archaeologist**, Arena Candide. Directed by Julien Real Salvatore, University of Denver.
- 2008: **Field Archaeologist**, Druze Marsh Archaeological and Paleoecological Research Project, Directed by April Nowell, University of Victoria.
- 2006: **Field school student**, McGill-Oulu University Field School.
Directed by Andre Costopoulos, McGill University.

MEMBERSHIP OF PROFESSIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

Society for American Archaeology, American Association of Physical Anthropologists, Dental Anthropology Association.

OSTEOLOGICAL AND BIOARCHAEOLOGICAL TRAINING

- 2012: ANA 7010: Human Gross Anatomy (9 credits), Wayne State University Medical School.
- 2012: 25th Annual Forensic Anthropology Course (06/11-06/15), Maryland Office of the Chief Medical Examiner.
- 2011: ASM 583: Bioarchaeology and Human Osteology (9 credits), ASU Kampsville Field Program.

2011: ANTHR BIO 477: Laboratory in Human Osteology (4 credits), University of Michigan.

PEDAGOGY AND CAREER DEVELOPMENT

2016: Rackham-CRLT May Seminar on Preparing Future Faculty, <http://www.crlt.umich.edu/programs/pff>

2016: Graduate Teaching consultant for the Center for Research on Learning and Teaching (CRLT).

2016: Experienced GSI – English Language Institute 994: College Teaching at the UM.

2016: Practice Teaching Facilitator – Engineering IA Teaching Orientation.

2016: Practice Teaching Facilitator and Session Facilitator – Winter CRLT Graduate Student Instructor (GSI) Teaching Orientation

2015: Facilitator for “Evaluating Student Writing” workshop, Philosophy Department.

2015: “Observing Classes & Gathering Midterm Student Feedback” – CRLT workshop.

2015: “Consulting with Graduate Student Instructors” – CRLT workshop.

2015: Graduate Teaching Consultant for the CRLT.

2015: Practice Teaching Facilitator and Session Facilitator – Fall CRLT GSI Teaching Orientation.

2015: “Advanced Strategies for Inclusive Teaching” – CRLT workshop.

2015: “Teaching Efficiently with Technology” – CRLT workshop.

2014 : University of Michigan Graduate Teacher Certificate, <http://crlt.umich.edu/um.gtc/description>

2013: SWC 993: Teaching Writing in the Disciplines – 1 credit course.

2013: “Engaging Students in Learning” – CRLT workshop.

2013: “Next Steps with Instructional Technology” – CRLT workshop.

2012: “Now That I Have It, What Grade Should I Give It? Evaluating Student Writing” – CRLT workshop.

2012: “Facilitating Classroom Discussions in the Social Sciences and the Humanities” – CRLT workshop.

DEPARTMENTAL SERVICE

2016: Honors Research Symposium Poster Judge, Dept. of Anthropology.

2016: Undergraduate Honors Thesis Writing Panel, Dept. of Anthropology.

2015: Career Path Panel, Undergraduate Archaeology Seminar

2015: Mentor for Honors Undergraduates, Dept. of Anthropology.

2015: Graduate Panel, Undergraduate Research Opportunity Program (UROP).

2015: Undergraduate Honors Thesis Writing Panel, Dept. of Anthropology.

2014: Honors Research Symposium Poster Judge, Dept. of Anthropology.

2013: Mentor for Honors Undergraduate, Dept. of Anthropology.

2011: Executive Committee Graduate Student Representative, Museum of Anthropological Archaeology.

2010: Secretary, Michigan Anthropology Graduate Association (Winter).

2009: Secretary, Michigan Anthropology Graduate Association (Fall).

PROFESSIONAL SERVICE

2016: Reviewer, [International Journal of Osteoarchaeology](#).

2015: Reviewer, [Journal of Anthropological Archaeology](#).

PUBLIC OUTREACH

2013-present: **Bone Broke Blog** (author): <http://www.bonebroke.org/>. I write engaging osteology, bioarchaeology, and anthropology posts with an active emphasis on pedagogy. As of September 2015, 1,700 page views/week, average. Mentioned in K. Meyers Emery and K. Killgrove (2015) “[Bones, Bodies and Blogs: Outreach and Engagement in Bioarchaeology](#)” *Internet Archaeology*: 39.

2016: 05/22 – Scientist Spotlight, station “Solving Puzzles Made of Bone” (Ruthven Museum of Natural History).

2016: 03/19 – Discovery Day: It’s About Time!, station “Solving Puzzles Made of Bone (RMNH).

2016: 03/12 – Portal to the Public Workshop 2: Prototyping Your Activity (RMNH).

2016: 02/12 – Portal to the Public Workshop One: How People Learn (RMNH).

2016: Science Communication Fellow, National Science Foundation Portal to the Public Program (RMNH).

2016: 02/12 – Archaeology Day (University of Michigan Museum of Anthropological Archaeology).

2015: 02/07 – Behind the Scenes Day (Ruthven Museum of Natural History).

2015: 01/27 – Archaeology Day (UMAA).

2014: 03/21 – Archaeology Day (UMAA).

2014: 02/09 – Behind the Scenes Day (RMNH).

2011: 02/13 – Behind the Scenes Day (RMNH).

2011: 02/11 – Archaeology Day (UMAA).

B5. Capacity of the Participating Organisations

University of Cambridge	
General Description	UCAM is one of the most renowned Research/Higher Education Institutes, frequently ranked amongst the top 5 in international academic rankings, e.g. ARWU and Shanghai Ranking. It has a long standing history of academic and scientific excellence backed up with rich culture, learning, research and creativity. Many affiliates of University of Cambridge have won Nobel Prizes for their significant advances. The University is also a major participant in European projects and was one of the top recipients of FP7 funding. The University Library is a copyright library and a major scholarly resource; it holds approximately 8M items.
Role and Commitment of key persons (supervisor)	Professor John Robb, Director of the Material Culture Laboratory, will supervise the MARBAL project. He is fully committed to the project and the future career development of the ER, seeing this as an excellent opportunity for archaeological research and skills training. He is fully aware of his responsibilities as Supervisor and more than 20 years' experience supervising postgraduate students and postdoctoral fellows (including FP7 and H2020 MSCA EFs) makes him ideal. Professor Robb expects to spend at least one hour each week in a supervisory capacity for the MARBAL project.
Key Research Facilities, Infrastructure and Equipment	The McDonald Institute has some of the best archaeology research facilities and infrastructure in Europe and attracts exceptional researchers to provide an intellectually stimulating environment for training and transfer of knowledge. It has state-of-the-art laboratories for zooarchaeology, archaeobotany, archaeogenetics, isotope analysis, biomechanics, geoarchaeology, material culture (with digital microscopes and abundant space for material analysis and group discussion), GIS and computing. The ER will have access to those relevant to the project with their world-class analytical infrastructure. The new Computational & Digital Archaeology Laboratory, to which all researchers are now affiliated, brings together researchers in GIS, 3d Photogrammetry, remote-sensing and computer simulation. It has access & support for use of the Darwin High Performance Computing Cluster, data storage and analysis on virtual machines managed by the University Information Service (UIS) and active collaboration with UIS for design, development and execution of bespoke computational analysis. Cambridge researchers are also supported by the copyright library collections. All lab and some library facilities are accessible on a 24-hour basis. Finally, the Institute houses excellent conference facilities which are available to the ER.
Independent research premises?	Yes. All research facilities are owned by the beneficiary and the research premises are wholly independent from other entities.
Previous Involvement in Research and Training Programmes	UCAM was involved in 336 FP7 projects: 163 Marie Curie grants, 16 ERC and 157 other EU funded projects, with a total value of £86.8m. The Institute was involved in 19 FP6 & FP7 projects: 13 MC IEFs, 5 ERC Grants & 1 ITN, 1 collaborative project. Several. 138 research and training projects have been funded in recent years by other UK and international sponsors (e.g. Royal Society, British Academy, Wellcome Trust, Leverhulme Trust, RCUK). Major ERC Advanced Grants include Prof Jones's AIG FOGLIP (249642), Prof Barker's AIG TRANSNAP (230421). MC IEFs include OVIPE (329526), AGRIVA (327203) & PALAEOHUNT (328502)).
Current involvement in Research and Training Programmes	The University of Cambridge is presently involved in 258 Horizon 2020 projects. This total consists of 133 MSCA grants (incl.102 IFs) 68 ERCs & 57 other EU funded projects The McDonald Institute currently hosts 6 H2020 MSC Fellows, with 4 to start shortly, 5 ERC grants (1 AIG, 2 COGs and 2 SIGs) and is a partner in a H2020 Twinning Project. McDonald staff are currently involved in 40 other externally-funded projects worth > £15.3m. Current Grants include MendtheGap (H2020 Widening Participation, Twinning Project 692249), Procon (ERC SIG 312603), HiddenFoods (ERC SIG 639286), TwoRains (CIG 648609) and "After the plague: health and history in medieval Cambridge" of which Prof Robb is PI and which is analysing the osteobiography of hundreds of skeletons from the St John's College Cambridge Medieval Cemetery, funded by the the Wellcome Trust (£1.2M).
Relevant Publications and/or research/innovation products	Robb, J.E. (2007). <i>The Early Mediterranean Village: Agency, Material Culture and Social Change in Neolithic Italy</i> . Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; Dobres M-A. & Robb J.E. (2000) <i>Agency in Archaeology</i> . London: Routledge; Robb J.E. (2013) Material culture, landscapes of action, and emergent causation. <i>Current Anthropology</i> DOI 10.1086/673859; J. Robb & O. Harris (eds.), (2013). <i>The Body in History: Europe from the Palaeolithic to the Future</i> . Cambridge University Press; Robb J.E. & Pauketat T. (2013). <i>Big Histories, Human Lives: Tackling Problems of Scale in Archaeology</i> (School for Advanced Research Advanced Seminar Series.) Santa Fe: SAR Press.

B6. Ethical Issues

Compliance with the relevant ethics provisions is essential from the beginning to the end of the action and is an integral part of research funded by the European Union within Horizon 2020.

Applicants submitting research proposals for funding within Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions in Horizon 2020 should demonstrate proactively to the REA that they are aware of and will comply with European and national legislation and fundamental ethical principles, including those reflected in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union¹² and the European Convention on Human Rights and its Supplementary Protocols¹³.

Please be aware that it is the applicants' responsibility to identify any potential ethical issue, to handle the ethical aspects of the proposal and to detail how these aspects will be addressed.

The Ethics Review Procedure in Horizon 2020

All proposals above threshold and considered for funding will undergo an Ethics Review carried out by independent ethics experts. When submitting a proposal to Horizon 2020, all applicants are required to complete an “**Ethics Issues Table (EIT)**” in the Part A of the proposal. Applicants who flag ethical issues in the EIT have to also complete a more in depth **Ethics Self-Assessment in Part B**.

The ethics self-assessment will become part of the Grant Agreement and may thus lead to binding obligations that may later on be checked during ethics checks, reviews and audits.

For more details, please refer to the H2020 “**How to complete your Ethics Self- Assessment**” guide¹⁴.

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/ethics_en.htm

¹² The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union: http://www.europarl.europa.eu/charter/pdf/text_en.pdf

¹³ http://www.echr.coe.int/Documents/Convention_ENG.pdf

¹⁴ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/ethics/h2020_hi_ethics-self-assess_en.pdf

Ethics Self-Assessment (Part B)

The Experienced Researcher (ER) responded positively to two questions in the Ethics section of Part A of the application. These questions involve: 1) the proposed research involves ancient human skeletal tissues (i.e. human tissues not from human embryos or foetuses); and 2) the use of local resources (specifically human remains).

As was described in relevant sections in Part A, the research proposed in this project will involve the analysis of human skeletal remains: in response to Research Objectives 1, 2 and 3, human skeletal remains recovered from the archaeological site of Rameț-Gugului will be transported to the McDonald Institute for Archaeological Research for analysis and sampling. These materials will be imported to the United Kingdom under a governmental permit (from the Department of Environment, Food and Rural Affairs – DEFRA) that relates to pathogen issues, not ethical issues. These skeletal tissues, including bones and teeth, date to approximately 2700-2200 BP, and they will be analysed for information on age, sex and pathology. The ancient skeletal material will also be sampled for carbon, nitrogen, oxygen and strontium isotopic research, and will be dated using AMS radiocarbon analysis. With the exception of the samples extracted for isotopic analysis and radiocarbon dating, all materials will be returned to Romania after the conclusion of the MARBAL project.

In keeping with the instructions outlined in the Template of Part B for composing an Ethics Self-Assessment, the following issues are addressed:

1) Export of Romanian archaeological material to the United Kingdom will follow pertinent national (Romanian) legislation: special permits will be issued by the relevant national (Romanian) authorities upon the positive recommendation/permission by excavators in Romania who are members of the Romanian National Registry of Archaeologists (*Registrul Arheologilor*). No permit issued by the United Kingdom authorities is needed to import this material to the United Kingdom.

2) There are no standard European Union ethical codes (either in the home country or in the UK) that pertain to the analysis of human remains that are several thousand years old. However, all material will be treated with due respect, making close reference to the British Association for Biological Anthropology and Osteoarchaeology (BABAO) code of ethics and code of practice (<http://www.babao.org.uk/index/ethics-and-standards>), as well as the Society for American Archaeology (SAA) Principles of Archaeological Ethics (<http://www.saa.org/AbouttheSociety/PrinciplesofArchaeologicalEthics/tabid/203/Default.aspx>). In every case, ethical approval will be obtained from the Department of Archaeology and Anthropology via the McDonald Institute Research Committee, and, when necessary, the School of Humanities and Social Sciences Ethics Committee at the University of Cambridge.

Thereby, the research proposed fully complies with EU and national legislation on ethics in research.

ENDPAGE

MARIE SKŁODOWSKA-CURIE ACTIONS

Individual Fellowships (IF)
Call: H2020-MSCA-IF-2016

PART B

“MARBAL”

“Mortuary Archaeology of the Rameț Bronze Age Landscape: Identity and inequality in early mining communities (2700-2200 BC)”

This proposal is to be evaluated as:

[Standard EF]

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